

ACADEMIC MOBILITY EXPERIENCES IN THE ASIA-PACIFIC REGION:
OPPORTUNITIES AND OBSTACLES

Iskandarova Dilnozakhan Ergashevna1,
Khushmurodova Mehriqiya Allayorovna1, I
Iskandarova Nilufar Ergshaevna2,
Iskanderova Irodakhon Ergashevna1

¹Tashkent Medical Academy Termiz Branch, Termiz, Uzbekistan

²Termiz State University, Termiz, Uzbekistan

ANNOTATION. This article analyzes academic mobility, one of the systems that has a positive effect on the professional and scientific development of students in the higher education system. The main focus is on studying the achievements of countries with high experience in this system and analyzing the necessary data.

Keywords: academic mobility, advantages and disadvantages of academic mobility, Asia-Pacific region experience, UMAP.

ikkkkkANNOTATION. In the framework of the project, academic mobility was analyzed as one of the systems that have a positive impact on the professional and scientific development of students in the higher education system. The main focus is on studying the achievements of countries with high experience in this system, the analysis of the necessary data.

Keywords: academic mobility, advantages and disadvantages of academic mobility, Asia-Pacific experience, UMAP..

Attracting foreign students to higher education organizations and ensuring the high level of competitiveness of trained personnel is one of the urgent issues today. Academic mobility is the practice of teaching, studying, conducting research abroad, and then returning the teacher or researcher to his/her main educational institution, which has a positive effect in internationally renowned universities and institutes. So it can be said without hesitation that academic mobility plays a positive role in ensuring the intellectual and professional maturity of the student. It is worth noting that within the framework of exchange programs held during the summer and winter holidays, participants can not only solve problems in their educational field (language learning, formation and development of professional skills), but also acquire international communication skills.

The purpose of the study. The scientific recommendations developed as a result of the research of the world experience in ensuring the academic mobility of students are widely used in higher education institutions.

Materials and discussion. Academic mobility is the movement of students and teachers of higher education institutions to another educational or scientific institution within or outside their country for a certain period of time for the purpose of study or teaching. Another definition of academic mobility is the ability to move students or faculty to another higher education institution, domestically or abroad, for a specific academic period for training or research. Students participating in academic mobility programs are usually divided into two groups: so-called free movers - students who go to other educational institutions based on their own initiative and self-

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-5

financing, and student exchange programs, for example, some department, faculty, educational institution or national level organizations (for example, Students participating in Erasmus, Nordplus or Fulbright).

As the Asia-Pacific region, one can understand the academic mobility in the countries of Asia and North and South America, which are part of the Pacific basin. Currently UMAP (**University Mobility in Asia and the Pacific**) seeks to provide greater understanding between members of each other's cultural, economic and social systems through cooperation and increased mobility of university students and staff.

University Mobility in Asia and the Pacific (UMAP) is an association of government and non-governmental organizations representing the higher education sector in Asia and the Pacific. The organization was established in 1991 to promote the exchange of university students and staff in the Asia-Pacific region. Pacific Ocean. In August 1998, the 6th meeting of the UMAP Reference Group was held in Bangkok, and the UMAP Constitution was adopted at the meeting (the Constitution was partially amended in 2001, 2005, 2013 and 2020).

The constitution aims to achieve a better understanding of the cultural, economic and social systems of other countries and regions in the region by expanding cooperation between higher education institutions in each country and region of the Asia Pacific region, and aims to increase the mobility of university students and staff.

UMAP aims to identify and remove barriers to university mobility; promotion of bilateral, multilateral and consortium agreements between universities of member countries and regions; set as a goal the development and support of the credit recognition and transfer system.

In 1999, the Australian Vice-Chancellor's Committee (AVCC) in collaboration with the Australian government organized a conference (Hong Kong in April 1999 and Canberra in September 1999) to invite university members to discuss educational cooperation in the Asia-Pacific region. Interested in Japan, Republic of Korea, Taiwan and Hong Kong. 18 countries participated in the conference in Canberra. A resolution was adopted to name the conference attended by these countries as "Reference Group Meeting" and the meeting became the 1st Reference Group Meeting of UMAP.

The International Secretariat of UMAP was established in April 1998 in Japan (within Komaba Campus, University of Tokyo) and moved to the 1st floor of Plaza Heisei, Tokyo International Exchange Center belonging to International Education Association. Japan (AIEJ) (now Japan Student Services Organization (JASSO)) in May 2001.

UMAP moved to Thailand in March 2006, Taiwan in January 2011, Japan again in January 2016 (within Toyo University), and Canada in January 2021.

The members of UMAP consist of representatives of national higher education institutions from each eligible country/territory and administrative region, forming a consortium of governments, universities and related organizations. In Japan, the UMAP Japan National Committee was established in cooperation with national, state and private university associations as the main participant in the national activities of UMAP.

Individuals are not eligible for UMAP membership, but individual universities from member countries/territories may join UMAP exchange programs.

As of 2021, the UMAP eligible countries/territories are: Countries/territories that pay an annual fee to the UMAP International Secretariat are full members of UMAP and form the UMAP Council.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-5

Australia, Bangladesh, Brunei, Cambodia, Canada, Chile, People's Republic of China, Ecuador, Fiji, Guam, Hong Kong, India, Indonesia, Japan, Republic of Korea, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Laos, Macau, Malaysia, Mexico, Mongolia, Myanmar, New Zealand, Papua New Guinea, Peru, the Philippines, Reunion Island, Russia, Samoa, Singapore, Taiwan, Thailand, Timor-Leste, USA, and Vietnam will participate as member states.

Under the UMAP Student Mobility Program, student exchange is enhanced and facilitated between individually accredited higher education institutions or consortia of institutions based on mutual acceptance of national accreditation determinations.

According to its purpose, UMAP implements semester programs and summer programs for student exchange and Research Net for academic cooperation. Participating universities are expected to waive tuition fees for UMAP semester exchange students and provide credit toward the students' home university degree for study during the exchange. In terms of research networking, researchers, academics and staff from participating universities of UMAP member countries/territories are encouraged to collaborate with each other in cross-border higher education, as well as explore opportunities to facilitate connections. and mutual understanding between cultures.

The UMAP Credit Transfer Scheme (UCTS) was developed to encourage student mobility and simplify the process of transferring credits received in exchange programs abroad.

The UCTS credit scoring scale makes it easy to convert credits between different scoring systems. It is based on the total teaching hours for the academic term (ie the length of a semester or short program) and the number of hours students are expected to participate in extracurricular activities, including the following activities. homework, reading assignments, group projects, final writing, and other program requirements. One UCTS credit hour is equal to 38-48 hours of student training, of which 13-16 hours are classroom instruction.

We studied the content, forms, methods and means of organizing academic mobility of students in US universities. Approaches to the Organization of Academic Mobility of Students in US Universities First of all, it should be noted that, as a rule, the principles of internationalization and openness are clearly expressed in the educational missions of US universities. For example, the mission of the University of Southern California states that men and women of all races, religions, and backgrounds have access to education. The mission of Harvard University is to spread good literature and art. and science can contribute to the education of the young generation of this country. The university strives to impart knowledge, encourage students to acquire competencies, encourage students to respect ideas and express them freely. Studying at the university allows students to develop their abilities, interests, and intellectual potential, and the support provided by the university is the basis for forming self-confidence and the habit of learning throughout life. The mission of Harvard University, the principle of lifelong learning is important in its activities. This principle, which applies to US universities, means that people can acquire or update knowledge that they once lacked during their lifetime. knowledge conditioned by personal, social, cultural or economic conditions, in accordance with the principles of completeness and transparency of information on the Columbia and Harvard University websites, information on study abroad programs, internships and summer schools is widely and easily presented. This information mainly covers four areas: non-academic administrative information (e.g. visa and residence permit issues), academic information (study period, class schedule, etc.), student expenditure information (i.e. the student's financial needs, his daily budget, housing). The main

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-5

countries where students come to study at Columbia University are China (the share of students from this country in the total number of foreign students is 18.3%), South Korea (9.7%), Canada (8.2%), India (7.4%) and France (3.8%). Among the fields of study at Columbia University, international students prefer engineering, public relations, business and social sciences. 79% of foreign students study at the master's and professional level, about 13% at the bachelor's level, and 4% at the American language programs. Lectures, seminars, and laboratory exercises are used to organize the training of students in academic mobility programs. At Columbia University. Tools for organizing the educational process include research resources and information technologies. Columbia University has the largest collection of educational materials in the United States. The university's 22 libraries have a wide range of resources and unique information for students and professors. Columbia University offers a number of opportunities to both its own students and students from other universities to study one of its programs outside the United States. Students are given the opportunity to study foreign languages at both the undergraduate and graduate levels, including some languages not available at other US universities.

Enrichment of the behavioral repertoire of the participants is carried out during the mastering of the training camp program, which allows them to communicate effectively with the residents. It refers to the means of stress relief, self-regulation and improvement of one's functional status; develop communication skills to overcome the language gap and master verbal and non-verbal behavior methods; awareness of differences in cultural dimensions to improve understanding between cultures. The unique perspective of the participant's lifestyle is an important dimension of integration into society and preparation for professional activity in a foreign environment.

At the same time, it is important that not only foreign guests adapt to the educational environment and characteristics of the host country, but also that local students and tutors adapt to the presence of foreigners.

All of the above problems are a solution to bring the positions closer to each other, an agreement, requires clarification and corrections. The Bologna process initiated extensive changes in the higher education system in Europe, which led to the convergence of European countries, their participation in the process of European integration and the enlargement of the European Union.

Summary It should be noted that the idea of creating a single European education system is effective and corresponds to today's realities, but the implementation of this system still requires serious improvement. The main barriers to academic mobility are cultural, social, economic and academic barriers. The Bologna process aims to try to reduce these barriers within the European Higher Education Area (EHEA). Studying in academic mobility programs allows students and graduates to improve their knowledge of a foreign language, deepen theoretical knowledge and practical skills, get to know the country better and meet foreign peers. Psychological barriers and challenges are related to aspects of student life such as homesickness or fear of new environment and social environment. Social difficulties usually mean problems communicating with family and friends. The degree to which students feel about certain challenges varies from case to case.

REFERENCES USED

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education";
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the concept

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-5

of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" dated October 8, 2019 No. PF-5847;

3. Ana Rute Cardoso, MP (2008). Demand for Higher Education Programs: The Impact of the Bologna Process. CESifo Economic Studies, 229–247.
4. Bray, ML (2007). Cross-border flows of students for higher education: Push–pull factors and motivations of mainland Chinese students in Hong Kong and Macau. Higher Educ vol 53 , 791–818.
5. Doreen Anne Rosenthal, JR (2008). The health and well-being of international
6. Gribble, C. (2008). Policy options for managing international student migration: the sending country's perspective. Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management vol 30 , 25–39.
7. Hataneke, S. (2004). Internationalism in Higher Education: A Review. London: Higher Education Policy Institute.
8. Line Verbick, VL (2007). International Student Mobility: Patterns and Trends. London: The Observatory on Borderless Higher Education.
9. Mohamed, B. (2010). Report Akhir Kajian Pelajar Antarabangsa Di Malaysia. Pulau Pinang: IPPTN.
10. Namgung, SU (2007). The role of returnees in internationalization at three
11. Korean universities. Proceedings of the 35th Annual Conference of the Australian and New Zealand Comparative International Education Society (ANZCIES) (pp. 172-189). Auckland: International Co-operation through Education.
12. OECD. (2009). OECD: Education At A Glance. Paris: OECD Publisher.
13. Olson, C. (2005). Comprehensive internationalization: from principles to practice. The Journal of Public Affairs, 51-73.
14. PEMANDU. (2010). Education NKEA Lab. Putrajaya: Performance Management Unit, Prime Minister's Department.
15. Stromquis, NP (2007). Internationalization as a response to globalization: Radical shifts in university environments. Higher Educ 53(1), 81–105.
16. Taylor, John. (2004). Toward a Strategy for Internationalization: Lessons and Practice from Four Universities. Journal of Studies in International Education 8(2), 149-173.
17. Young, R. (2002). University internationalization: its meanings, rationales and implications. Intercultural Education 13(1), 81-96.
18. Bogoslovsky I.V., Pisareva S.A., Tryapitsyna A.P. Akademicheskaya mobility: realization in Bolonskom process: Method. posobie dlya studentsov. — Spb.: Izd-vo RGPU im. A.I. Hertsen, 2007. — 55 p.
19. Khajieva I. et al. Foreign language competence formation of the future teacher of vocational education in the information and educational environment //European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine. - 2020. - T. 7. – no. 2. - S. 360-365.
20. Agishev RR Academic mobility programs: features and opportunities // Diffusion of the Bologna Process: from declarations to implementation in practice: In 3 hours, Part 2. Trends in the development of the Bologna process, its tools and implementation experience. - Kazan: KSTU im. AN Tupolev, 2008.-- P. 103-110.
21. Kenzhaeva Kh. P. CRITERIA OF CIVIL CULTURE IN THE INTERPRETATION OF EASTERN PHILOSOPHY // Academic research in educational sciences. - 2021. - T.2. - No. 3.
22. Khajieva I. et al. Foreign language competence formation of the future teacher of vocational education in the information and educational environment // European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine. - 2020. - T. 7. - No. 2. - S. 360-365.